

Opportunities and Challenges for Private Universities in India

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ABSTRACT

A State Private University is established through a State/Central Act by a sponsoring body viz., a society registered under the Societies Registration Act 1860, or any other corresponding law for the time being in force in a State or a Public Trust or a Company registered under Section 25 of the Companies Act, 1956. In a country like India, where higher education is largely inaccessible and unaffordable to a substantial chunk of youngsters, the possibilities that open up before a private university is enormous. While at the same time, it is supposed to provide quality education and beat the competitors, resource constraints and establishing brand image looms large as detriments. In this paper we have looked into the challenges and opportunities of private Universities for imparting Higher Education in terms of Establishment, Admission, Designing courses and Curriculum, Innovations in teaching and learning processes, Research and development, Industry and external collaborations, Usage of ICT, Student support and Progression, Expansion to global market, Governance, Leadership and Management, Innovations and Best practices etc. The Advantages, Benefits, Constraints, and Disadvantages of Private Universities for its stakeholders like students, faculty members, parents, industries and society are also discussed. The opportunities and challenges of National Institutional Ranking framework under stated criteria are analyzed.

Keywords : Opportunities for Private universities, Challenges for private universities.

I. Introduction

India has one of the largest and diverse educational systems in the world. About thirty per cent of its population are youngsters who are the potential candidates to opt higher education but presently only 18% of its university age population is getting higher education facility.

Though the higher education opportunity is not confirmed to all deserved aspirants, privatization, widespread expansion, increased autonomy to higher educational institutions and introduction of programs in new and emerging areas have improved access to higher education. At the same time it also led to widespread concern on the quality and relevance of the higher education. To address these concerns, the National Policy on Education (NPE, 1986) and the Programme of Action (PoA, 1992) that spelt out strategic plans for the policies, advocated the establishment of independent Private Universities. As a result, University Grants Commission (UGC) allowed establishing Private Universities by State Governments in the form of Private University Act passed by the State Assembly. A State Private University is a university established through a State/Central Act by a sponsoring body viz. A Society registered under the Societies Registration Act 1860, or any other corresponding law for the time being in force in a State or a Public Trust or a Company registered under Section 25 of the Companies Act, 1956. Private Universities are different in size, enrolment, course offered, funding authority, financial and managerial capacity. In a country like India, where higher education is largely inaccessible and unaffordable to a substantial chunk of youngsters, the possibilities that open up before a private university is enormous. While at the same time, it is supposed to provide quality education and beat the competitors, resource constraints and establishing brand image looms large as detriments.

Throughout the world, Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) function in a dynamic environment. The need to expand the system of higher education, the impact of technology on the educational delivery, the increasing private participation in higher education and the impact of globalization (including liberal cross-border and transnational educational imperatives), have necessitated marked changes in the Indian higher education system. These changes and the consequent shift in values have been taken into cognizance by the objectives of Private Universities.

Higher education in India has largely been the preserve of the government till recently in terms of both funding and provision of education. In the 2000s the government of India realized the need for setting up private universities as it was clear that the public universities in India would not be able to meet the increasing demand for higher education. It was a milestone in the history of higher education. Private universities are established by philanthropic, religious, and private organizations and foundations, and by not-for-profit organizations. At present there are 165 private universities in India. Some are providing

world standard education. These quality institutions have prepared a ground to compete each other about the quality of education they are providing (Rajesh 2014).

The various challenges for Higher Education in India are :

- Need to double capacity – not just in terms of seat count but “quality” seats count.
- Deregulate education in India.
- Remove the “Not for profit” requirement to facilitate the investment from private sector.
- Industry and Academia connect necessary to ensure curriculum and skills in line with requirements.
- Skill building is really very crucial to ensure employability – Academia to understand and make sure – knowledge + skills+ global professional skills = good jobs.
- Industry and students are expecting specialized courses to be offered so that they get the latest and best in education and they are also industry ready and employable.
- Too much power vested in single institutions that regulate e.g AICTE control on policy, licensing, funding, curriculum etc. Need to disintegrate to perform specific key functions.
- Some industry-academic connection programs not working out as expected – eg. summer training for MBA students – most of them given dummy projects and are avoided while on board. Industry needs to get involved to support institutions.
- Vocational and Diploma courses need to be made more attractive to facilitate specialized programs being offered to students.

The need of higher education facility to cater the desired large population, with diversity in curriculum to provide desired knowledge, skills, and professional skills, many more new universities are required. The Opportunities for New Universities are :

- There is an ample opportunity for establishing a Private University in India by Private sector due to low quality higher education service provided by Public sector Institutions.
- Also the Private Universities with state-of-art infra-structure, facilities and highly qualified faculty members can attract International students from developed and developing countries due high quality education at low cost.
- Hence there is an opportunity to establish high-tech Universities in India.

II. Private Universities in India

(1) UGC Norms on Private Universities :

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As per the UGC Circular in June 2009, the UNIVERSITY GRANT COMMISSION (UGC) has allowed to start Private Universities which are established by the Acts of the Legislatures of different States. It has imposed following norms in case of Private Universities :

1. These State Private **Universities are not competent to affiliate colleges and start off-campus centre(s)** beyond the territorial jurisdiction of their State.
2. These universities are **competent to award degrees** as specified by UGC under Section 22 of the UGC Act and with the approval of the statutory councils, wherever required **through their main campus**. Wherever the approval of the statutory council is not a pre-requisite to start a programme, the universities are required to maintain the minimum standards regarding academic and physical infrastructure as laid down by the concerned statutory council.
3. It is also informed that private universities **cannot affiliate an institution/college**. They cannot establish off campus centre(s) beyond the **territorial jurisdiction of the concerned State**. However, they can establish off-campus centre(s) within the concerned State after their existence of five years and with the prior approval of the University Grants Commission. **So far, UGC has not approved any off campus centre(s) of any Private University.**
4. Approval letters for course under distance mode should clearly state that the course has been approved by the Joint Committee UGC, AICTE and DEC and the **approval letter should be jointly signed** by Secretary UGC , Member Secretary, AICTE and Director, DEC as per the provision laid down under clause 9 of the MOU signed by UGC, AICTE and DEC.
5. Students/Public at large are advised to go through www.ugc.ac.in carefully **before taking admission** in any of the below State Private Universities and report the matter to Secretary, UGC on finding any violation of the above provisions.

Jeelani et.al. (2014), have published a paper on “Private Universities : Challenges and Opportunities in Higher Education” in which they made a SWOT analysis of private Universities, Establishment and recognition of private Universities by UGC, and suggestions for strengthening the quality of higher education in private Universities.

(2) Advantages for Private Universities :

- Academic Freedom : Removal of obsolete
- Customized Program : More specializations
- Quick technology adoption : Online support
- Global Reach : Attracting students from abroad
- Focus on Research : faculty utilization

- Quality through competition : Enhanced choice for students
- Contribution to Economic growth : Job creation
- Extended opportunities for aspirants of quality higher education
- Opportunity for doing research in various innovative higher education models to make it effective & attractive
- Academic freedom to create all-round leaders in multi-disciplinary areas.
- Identifying and creating experts in new futuristic areas through starting new programmes

- Fostering innovations in examination system
- Connecting and networking industries with innovators
- Freedom to industry and foreign university collaboration for internship and exchange of students & faculty
- Freedom for educational reforms

(3) Objectives of Private Universities :

- a) to create high levels of intellectual abilities
- b) to establish state-of-the-art facilities for education and training
- c) to create centers of excellence for research and development
- d) to provide consultancy to the industries & public organization
- e) to impart value and ethic based education through national and international collaboration
- f) to focus on new models of education like training including online and distance education along with traditional education system
- g) to stress the importance of multi-disciplinary and trans-disciplinary education and research in various areas of science, engineering, technology, philosophy, and culture.
- h) To develop scientific, technological, cultural and traditional heritage of the people of the society through continuous education.
- i) To create effective trainers to train human resource of the world.

Based on above objectives, private universities have power and freedom to design various academic & research programmes which include :

- Formal Education
- Training
- Online Education
- Distance Education

- Research & Development
- Consultation
- Education programmes for all-round development
- Earn while learn courses
- Learn while you earn courses
- Dual degree programmes
- Integrated programmes
- Residential programmes
- Evening & week end programmes

III. Opportunities & Challenges of Private Universities

(1) Establishment :

Private universities in general provide better infrastructure to their stake holders compared to many public universities due to the reason to establish better brand image.

(a) Opportunities :

- Opportunity to provide world class infrastructure based campus
- Providing campus residences to support more faculty involvement in teaching-learning and research activities.
- Opportunity to create wealth
- Opportunity to establish name, brand and meaningful investment
- Opportunity to collaborate with foreign universities, work as a franchisee of established foreign universities due to existing world class infrastructure
- Opportunity to overall development of the region
- Opportunity to create jobs for local people
- Opportunity to provide higher education and research services to the youngsters of the country
- Opportunity to contribute in national development.
- Opportunity to innovate in the field of higher education through various reforms using the existing autonomy.

(b) Challenges :

- Initial investment and development
- Creating brand

- Attracting highly qualified and dedicated faculty members
- Student acceptance and admission for initial years of establishment
- Formation of strategy to face competition by established public universities
- Challenges of expansion of campus due to government policies & regulations
- Challenge to create competitive & innovative curriculum to attract students
- Challenge to develop industry collaborations & foreign university collaborations etc.
- Challenges in facing competitions like online education and distance education

(2) Student Admission :

Student admission is core business of private universities. Since student fee is the primary source of income to private universities, they have to focus on demand creation for admissions of various courses. Initially they have to focus on starting popular courses which have good demand in the job market. Based on developing attractive education model which is student centric, a private university can improve its perception among student community. Formulating and implementing admission strategy by reserving appropriate budgetary fund to attract students from other states of the country and from potential countries is a challenging task.

(a) Opportunities :

- Opportunity to attract students from developed countries due to large difference in fee structure for higher studies in developed countries and India
- Opportunities to attract students from other developing countries due to the fact of providing high quality intensive education a nominal, affordable cost.
- Opportunity to implement innovative marketing strategy and utilize all available channels of advertisement and freedom to collaborate with various admission agencies
- Opportunity to add values to the university courses by means of innovations and best practices like dual degree opportunity, earn while learn opportunity, providing skill development programmes, better national & international placements, foreign visits/exchange programmes etc.

(b) Challenges :

- Marketing expenditure
- Providing unique, student friendly, futuristic, and industry/job market oriented model

- Identifying student need
- Providing student friendly services to enhance popularity of the courses and university
- Conducting online entrance examination for admission or identifying & conducting entrance examinations in various centres of the country and abroad
- Planning the criteria to offer scholarships and discounts for meritorious students
- Identifying, designing & offering new futuristic job oriented courses in UG & PG level
- Attractive admission strategy & propaganda
- Involving all stake holders in admission process based on various incentives
- Providing online information through an attractive website & using online advertisements effectively
- How university can use its existing students and alumni in improving admission & brand building

(3) Designing courses & Curriculum :

One of the advantages of private university is of having autonomy in designing courses and effective curriculum for them. This also include deciding teaching methods, participation of industry experts, number of subjects in each semester, weightage to be given to hard subjects, soft subjects, skill development subjects and practical/field sessions in each course.

(a) Opportunities :

- Opportunity to design high demand & futuristic course with further innovation
- Identifying effective curriculum for each courses in collaboration with top level universities & industry experts
- Opportunity to provide dual degree programmes with foreign universities
- Many electives, specializations and student self-tailored courses can be provided to make each graduate unique for industry/society
- Offering crash courses to avoid wastage of students precious time in the campus

(b) Challenges :

- Designing widely acceptable but innovative courses & curriculum
- How to integrate research components & industrial trainings in the curriculum

- How to design courses which will give multiple benefits to the students and keep them engaged in academic activities
- Increasing the number of customized electives in every course courses so that every student in a course is super specialized in different areas
- Based on identifying courses & designing curriculum, how all stakeholders can be satisfied.

(4) Innovations in Teaching & Learning processes :

Diversity of learners in respect of their background, abilities and other personal attributes will influence the extent of their learning. The teaching-learning modalities of the universities are rendered to be relevant for the learner group. The learner-centered education through appropriate methodologies facilitates effective learning. Teachers provide a variety of learning experiences, including individual and collaborative learning. The teachers employ interactive and participatory approach creating a feeling of responsibility in learning and makes learning a process of construction of knowledge.

(a) Opportunities :

- Inventing & adopting new models of teaching which is more effective than conventional.
- Researching in teaching – learning process to evolve ideal model based on autonomy to private universities.
- Giving emphasis to participatory learning & online learning.
- Providing opportunity for multi-field specialization and multidisciplinary curriculum to enhance student interest and involvement.

(b) Challenges :

- New innovative models of teaching – learning may not give expected results
- Effective utilization of online/e-component in teaching- learning process by using relevant technology
- Acceptance of innovations by all stakeholders and country government
- Challenge on making learning a process of construction of knowledge

(5) Research & Development :

Private universities can become successful only if they focus on research in individual subjects/specified areas and multi-disciplinary areas. Investment in research is the primary

requirement to attract national and international students for admission. Private university faculties have more freedom to collaborate, seek for fund and start new programmes which have research components. By incorporating research content in UG and PG course curriculum, students can be utilized to get extra-ordinary research output. Private universities have opportunity to organize various seminars, workshops and conferences frequently to promote research in contemporary areas.

(a) Opportunities :

- Opportunity to focus on research by reserving substantial part of their funds on research and development which enhances the name, fame and admission
- Freedom to appoint faculty members who have research inclination & interest irrespective of vacancies in the department
- Opportunity to generate research fund through industry collaboration, public contribution and government agencies

(b) Challenges :

- Creating interest in research among faculties and students
- Attracting research funds from industry collaboration, public contribution and government agencies
- Enhancing research contribution in terms of publications, IPR, patents etc.

(6) Industry & Foreign Collaborations :

Private university should strive for formal agreement/ understanding various Higher Educational Institutions or agencies for training/student exchange/faculty exchange/research/resource sharing etc.

(a) Opportunities :

- Course design based on industry collaboration so that industry specific customized training can be imparted. This will eliminate further training in industry.
- Industry directed courses eliminates obsolescence in higher education system
- Collaboration with foreign universities for promotion of research, further studies of students, faculty exchange. Dual degree programmes etc.

(b) Challenges :

- Developing relationship with different industries
- Identifying industry requirements

- Persuading industries about importance and benefits of collaboration with education institutes
- Identifying suitable established foreign university in different countries for collaboration & mutual benefits
- Active involvement of administration, faculty members to fulfill the objectives of collaboration
- Student acceptance of such collaborations

(7) Usage of ICT :

Advances in information communication technology & internet supports universities to improve their overall services to stakeholders. All the information pertaining to admission, curriculum, university calendar, Faculty, teaching & learning processes, examinations, special training opportunities, student & faculty notices, competitive exam tips, campus placement opportunities, student activities, research information, sports & games information, student & faculty achievements should be available in university website. The university should provide information to its students and faculty through intranet and information to other stakeholders like parents, industries, and alumni through extranet. The website of the university must contain updated information about quality services, innovations made, important placement details and research contributions made by the departments/schools of the university.

(a) Opportunities :

- Using ICT for organizational benefits
- Developing an interactive website to provide useful information to public
- Developing intranet for internal information sharing with students & faculty members
- Developing extranet for relevant information sharing with other stakeholders

(b) Challenges :

- Investment on ICT innovations
- Challenges of changes in technology & ICT models
- User friendly modules
- Information security

(8) Student support & Progression :

Facilitating mechanisms like guidance cell, placement cell, grievance redressal cell and

welfare measures support students development in the campus. Specially designed inputs are provided to the needy students with learning difficulties. Provision should be made for bridge and value added courses in relevant areas. University should develop well structured, organized guidance and counseling system in place.

(a) Opportunities :

- To provide world class infrastructure and teaching & learning aids
- Highly educated & talented faculty members
- Practice oriented course structure

(b) Challenges :

- Facilitating the students to improve the competency
- Monitoring & measuring the students progress
- Achieving expected student progression

(9) Evaluation Process and Reforms :

Issues related to assessment of teaching, learning and evaluative processes and reforms, should be adopted to increase the efficiency and effectiveness of the university. One of the purposes of evaluation is to provide development-inducing feedback. It should also help the teacher to plan appropriate activities for enhancing student performance. The qualitative dimension of evaluation is in its use for enhancing the competence of students. Innovative evaluation process is to gauge the knowledge and skills acquired at various levels of the programmes.

(a) Opportunities :

- Reforms & improvements in teaching-learning processes based on student feedback
- Improvements in service model based on other stakeholders feedback & suggestions
- Planning, designing, and organizing various activities for enhancing student performance and competency

(b) Challenges :

- Identifying best evaluation method
- Collecting genuine feedback without bias
- Acceptance of reforms by all stakeholders

(10) Expansion to Global Market :

Private universities should strive to become global either by attracting and admitting students from many countries through a suitable admission strategy or by starting branches or subsidiaries in other countries. If the private university is equipped to provide international standard education & research it can attract foreign students easily which also depends on other infrastructure & social life in the campus and the country.

(a) Opportunities :

- Admission of global students in the campus
- Providing online education to the aspirants all over the world
- Arranging international placement to the graduates
- Opening branches of the university in other countries
- Collaboration/tie-up with foreign universities for student exchange
- Foreign industry visits

(b) Challenges :

- Formulation of marketing strategy for advertisement and attracting global students
- Popularising courses & university for online education
- Bringing international and multinational companies to the campus for student placement
- Finding international partners for global expansion
- Collaboration/tie-up with foreign universities for research collaboration & student exchange
- Tie-up with national & international companies & agencies for industry visits
- Tie-up with international banks & financial institutions for students education loan

(11) Governance, Leadership and Management :

Effective leadership by setting values and participative decision- making process is important not only to achieve the vision, mission and goals of the university but also in building the organizational culture. The formal and informal arrangements in the university to co-ordinate the academic and administrative planning and implementation reflects the universities efforts in achieving its vision. The leadership provides clear vision and mission. The functions of the university and its academic and administrative units are governed by the principles of participation and transparency. Formulation of development objectives, directives and guidelines with specific plans for implementation by aligning the academic and

administrative aspects improves the overall quality of the university provisions.

(a) *Opportunities* :

- Focused vision, development through team work
- Participative management and teamwork
- Improving quality of education & research

(b) *Challenges* :

- Ambitious & experienced leadership
- Planning, co-ordination, Motivation & dedication by university officials
- Specific plans of growth & expansion
- Quest for excellence
- Funding for improving quality of education & research

(12) Innovations & Best practices :

The focus on the innovative efforts of private university helps its academic excellence. An innovative practice could be a pathway created to further the interest of the student and the university, for internal quality assurance, inclusive practices and stakeholder relationships.

(a) *Opportunities* :

- Innovations in admission process
- Innovations in course planning & curriculum design
- Innovation in student assessment and examination systems
- Innovations in teaching & learning
- Innovations in resource management
- Innovations in student support
- Innovations in effective utilization of ICT for quality education
- Innovations in stakeholder relationship
- Innovations in online global education
- International standard best practices
- Green Campus and effective energy management

(b) *Challenges* :

- Innovative strategy for international admissions
- Optimum energy & other resources utilization

- Better stakeholder relationship
- Creating & maintaining best practices from faculty and students

(13) Social Responsibility :

Learning activities have a visible element for developing sensitivities towards community issues, gender disparities, social inequity etc. and in inculcating values and commitment to society. Mutual benefit from affiliation and interaction with groups or individuals who have an interest in the activities of the university and the ability to influence the actions, decisions, policies, practices or goals of the organization. University should identify & implement processes and strategies that relevantly sensitize students to the social issues and contexts.

(a) Opportunities :

- Identifying and inculcating core values in students & faculties
- Through various forms, active participation in social development
- Contributing to the society through community services & corporate social responsibility

(b) Challenges :

- Sensitizing students to the social issues and contexts
- Organizing community development programmes with the support of neighbouring NGO's.

IV. Private University & its Stakeholders

With changes in education scenario, the self financing private universities are considered as service industry. In this service industry, students are customer stakeholders, industries & society are the beneficiary stakeholders, Faculty members are service providing stakeholders and parents of students are investing stakeholders. Such a new model of private university is shown in figure 1.

(1) Students :

Students are primary stakeholders of the university. They are patrons of university existence. The advantages, benefits, constraints, and disadvantages of Private university system in the frame of reference of students are listed below :

Fig. 1 : New Model of Stakeholders of Private University.

(a) *Advantages :*

- Enhanced opportunity to do higher education and research in their interested area.
- Access to quality education opportunity for academically medium performers to prove their ability at later stage.
- The students who can pay more fees for quality education need not search to get admission in foreign universities.
- A place where students can get world class infrastructure, friends of comparable status, academic and peer group networking, care, support and enjoyment.

(b) *Benefits :*

- Quality care at affordable price
- Accessibility to new and innovative models of education to improve overall development
- Better placement support owing to continuous soft skills trainings.
- Life-long support from the alma-mater through active alumni association.
- Additional support during studies in the form of printed study materials, exchange programmes, involvement in research projects.
- Students will get more confidence due to the quality and international exposure of their faculty.
- Students will improve their communication ability and confidence based on the professional atmosphere in the campus.
- Opportunity to participate in extracurricular activities
- Better job opportunities through inviting more industries to the campus.
- Integrated programmes, dual degree or semester abroad programmes opportunity
- Continuous monitoring for better academic performance

- Innovations in examination system decreases tension provoke active learning and problem solving ability.

(c) *Constraints* :

- Comparatively high fee structure
- Pressure for targets on curricular, co-curricular and extra-curricular activities.

(d) *Disadvantages* :

- Comparatively high cost during course duration in the campus
- Burden to the parents if admission is not through scholarship.
- Demand for competition in student performance

(2) Faculty Members :

Faculty members are the back bone of quality education provided by private universities. The future of private universities exists based on their quality & innovative services to mould students from raw stones into sparkling diamonds. The advantages, benefits, constraints, and disadvantages of Private university system in the frame of reference of faculty members are listed below :

(a) *Advantages* :

- Opportunity to implement new courses, futuristic curriculum, innovative examination system
- Competitive environment in terms of curriculum design, teaching and research
- International facilities in university campus,
- Encouragement for research, publications, patents and IPR
- Encouragement for national & international collaboration
- Opportunity to involve in admission process, brand building activities, administration based additional skills

(b) *Benefits* :

- Better pay & perks based on qualification & experience
- Recognition for hard work, innovations, and breakthroughs in research.
- Institutional support for research, publications, patent registration and book publication
- Additional earning opportunity through additional work
- Opportunity for undertaking consultancy for industries and other agencies
- Opportunity to collaborative research with national & international agencies
- Encouraging atmosphere for personal and academic growth

- Team work, opportunity in multi disciplinary research areas due to qualified and experienced peer group

(c) *Constraints* :

- Pressure on performance
- High competition
- Constraints of a self financing institution

(d) *Disadvantages* :

- Unhealthy competition among the faculty members
- Pressure for publications, patents, improving teaching models
- Continuous assessment
- Demand on performance

(3) Parents :

Parents are investing hope and money in private universities by paying substantially high fees expecting great returns in the form of fulfilling their dreams of making their wards into successful and useful citizen of the society. The advantages, benefits, constraints, and disadvantages of Private university system in the frame of reference of parents are listed below :

(a) *Advantages* :

- World class education on door step
- Opportunity to provide quality higher education to children
- Build professionals worthy of high profile jobs

(b) *Benefits* :

- Fulfilling their dreams of making their ward into successful and beneficial citizen of the society
- Recognition in the society
- Better job with lucrative salary to the children
- Children are prepared to face competitive exams through intensive and concurrent training programmes

(c) *Constraints* :

- Limited resources to meet the cost
- Challenges of a slowly growing brand image

(d) *Disadvantages* :

- Higher expenditure/investment for children education

(4) Industry & Society :

The industries are the recruiters. Society is the beneficiary of graduate entrepreneurs. Based on innovative training provided by the private universities, the new recruits in industries, become better decision makers and formulate effective strategies to improve & expand the business and convert it as sustainable profit making entity. Successful entrepreneurs identify new business opportunities, and create jobs for economic development of the society. The advantages, benefits, constraints, and disadvantages of Private university system in the frame of reference of industries and society are listed below :

(a) Advantages :

- Autonomy and freedom in designing courses
- Opportunity to share industry requirements to improve employability skills
- Opportunity to share executives experience and suggestions to groom young professionals
- Opportunity to collaborate with private universities easier than with Government universities
- Opportunity to start collaborative courses as per industry requirement

(b) Benefits :

- Quality professionals to man responsible positions.
- Help from students who are doing projects in industry
- Earn while learn program encourages self reliance.
- Projects relevant to industry requirement receive priority
- Community engagement and social service activities are initiated

(c) Constraints :

- Responsibility as mentors for students of innovative private universities

(d) Disadvantages :

- Student interactions may affect industry productivity.

V. National Institutional Ranking Framework

National Institutional Ranking Framework developed by the Ministry of Human Resource Development, Govt. of India has identified various criteria and parameters that have global appeal e.g. research output, research impact, learning environment, etc. has also considered parameters like infrastructure, facilities for differently-abled persons, percentage of students from other states and other countries; percentage of women students and faculty, and

percentage of economically and disadvantaged students. The framework has also given weightage to the sports and extra-curricular facilities available in the campuses of universities, which, supports on overall development of a student in a university. Here we have analysed the opportunities and challenges of various criteria and parameters of national institutional ranking framework for Private universities [9].

(1) Opportunities

(a) Teaching, Learning and Resources :

1. Faculty – Student Ratio

Private universities have freedom to increase the number of faculties as per desired level unlike Govt. funded universities. Hence private universities have opportunity to raise faculty strength to the optimum requirement level of 1:10 ratio. This will improve the international ranking opportunity for private universities. Based on increase in faculty ratio, they also get freedom to charge higher fees from students without being affected by Government restrictions.

2. Faculty with PhD and Experience

Private universities have no restrictions in appointing highly qualified faculty members with Ph.D. and experience by paying lucrative salary unlike public universities. Since public universities have to follow govt. reservation policies and fixed pay structure along with fixed cadres as per regulations. This opportunity of private university will give a competitive edge in appointing doctorates and similarly qualified faculties with an average minimum of 15 years experience. This will further improve the international ranking opportunity for private universities.

3. Library and Laboratory Facilities

Based on financial freedom of private universities, they can invest substantially in library books, institutional publications, physical and on-line journals etc. For similar reason, they have opportunity to invest state-of-art laboratories by their own investments and through collaboration with industries. Such autonomy in financial investment makes them to compete with public universities and enhance their success in international institutional rankings.

4. Sports Facilities and Extra-Curricular Activities

The financial capability and freedom to invest without any budget restrictions enable private universities to divert more resources towards sports and extra-curricular activities which will add to the existing score of ranking of private universities compared to public universities.

(b) Research Productivity, Impact and IPR :

1. Publications :

Private universities have freedom to encourage research and publications by providing research encouragement in the form of university project fundings and research awards. This also include fixing minimum targets for each and every faculty member so that have opportunities to increase average quality publications compared to public universities which cannot give targets based on government policies.

2. Citations :

Based on above reasons private universities have opportunity to increase quality of publications by its highly qualified, innovative, experienced, large number of faculty members, compared to public universities which have restrictions in appointment and encouragement for quality research.

3. IPR :

Private universities have freedom to start a patent division in the university to educate and support faculty members in patenting their IPR so that faculty members can save their precious time wasting on technical requirements of patenting. Private universities also have freedom to announce incentives and promotions to the faculties to encourage them to develop new ideas and improved processes to file patents.

(c) Graduation Outcome :**1. University Exam Performance :**

Private universities have opportunities to make innovations in curriculum, teaching-learning process, and examination reforms to see that there will be higher rate of success in university examination.

2. Competitive Examination :

Private universities have opportunity to include regular training sessions to students on answering multiple choice questions in all subjects in the curriculum itself, which will increase the confidence of students to face competitive exams to go for higher education or to get better job.

(d) Outreach and Inclusivity :**1. Continuing Education, Services :**

Private universities have better opportunities to maintain alumni association and continued communication with alumni and conduct continuing online education programmes in chosen area of further development. Private universities also conducts training programmes to industry people, MDP programmes, FDP programmes, many conferences and workshops compared to public universities.

2. Percentage of Students from Other States & Countries :

By adopting strategic marketing propaganda, private universities have better opportunity for attracting local, outer state and other country students for their innovative and attractive courses.

3. Percentage of Women Students and Faculty :

By appointing more women faculties due to freedom of appointment, by providing safety & security in the campus, and by announcing more scholarships/discounts for women students private universities have opportunity to attract more women students and faculty to increase their average percentage to 50%.

4. Percentage of Economically and Socially Disadvantaged Students :

Private universities have freedom to announce large discounts or free seats for a category of students which will allow them admit even 50% economically and socially disadvantaged students to various courses.

5. Facilities for Differently Aabled Persons :

Private universities are recently established entities in India compared to public universities and hence they have opportunity to focus on special infrastructural facilities like ramps, lifts, disabled friendly toilets while constructing the buildings to support physically challenged people.

(e) Perception

1. Process for Peer Rating in Category :

By means of participating various university ranking frameworks conducted by various agencies, quality initiatives through ISO standards, collaboration with industries, innovative value additions, high lighting the academic programmes in news papers, private universities have opportunity to get better ratings in Peer rating category.

2. Application to Seat Ratio :

Due to innovative marketing and continuous advertisement by investing a part of their annual budget, private universities have ability to attract more applications to their courses compared to public universities which have regional restrictions. With a separate marketing team and strategy,, private universities have opportunity to attract more students from other states and other countries too.

(2) Challenges :

(a) Teaching, Learning and Resources :

1. Faculty – Student Ratio

Increasing faculty-student ratio up to 1 : 10 or more will increase financial burden on private university. Since it will not get any financial support from the government, and depends on fee collection from the students, the fee to be charged for payment quota students will be

heavy and is a real challenge to the university. However, public universities will not face such problems due to the fact that they receive large amount of funds from state and central governments.

2. Faculty with PhD and Experience

Getting good number of intelligent teaching faculty members with Ph.D. and experience in different futuristic areas is real challenge. By offering high pay-scales, facilities and perks, private university can attract highly talented faculties which will in turn enhance the expenditure of the university. Keeping the experienced faculty members active in research is another challenge for private universities even though they announce target for individual faculty research, publications and patents.

3. Library and Laboratory Facilities

Since the ranking score on library books & journals is based on current year investment and not on quantity of stock accumulated from several years, private universities have challenge in investing more from current year budget for physical and online books and journals. Establishing university publication division and own sophisticated press is challenge to private universities to add values and increase the books in the library. Similarly up-grading latest tech equipments and computers in the laboratories by attracting external funds and also allocating internal budgetary funds is a challenge.

4. Sports Facilities and Extra-Curricular Activities

The greatest challenge for private universities is creating world class sports and games facilities. Since the features like sports facilities area per student, sports budget and number of top performances of students in national and international sports events will be counted in this category ranking, private universities have to reserve substantial amount of their annual investment & efforts on this area.

(b) Research Productivity, Impact and IPR :

1. Publications :

Faculty publications indexed in Scopus, Web of Science, Google Scholar and Indian Citation Index will be counted for assessment. Appointing such competent faculties, supporting them to establish sophisticated research labs, encouraging them to collaborate with national & international level institutions, attracting research funds from government agencies and industries, creating research targets, attracting talented research scholars and announcing attractive incentives for quality publications are present challenges for private universities to top ranking which in turn, attract more talented students for admission.

2. Citations :

By encouraging and supporting researchers to publish top ranked journals with high impact factors, open access journals, and indexed in Scopus, Web of Science, Google Scholar, will enhance the possibility of increase in citations which will in turn increase national ranking score for this category. Private universities have challenges to encourage & motivate quality research and publications which will increase annual citation.

3. IPR :

Publishing books with established national & international publishers, conference proceedings with ISBN numbers, registering patents at national level & international level are challenges for private universities since it requires high level intellectual capital in the campus.

(c) Graduation Outcome :

1. University Exam Performance :

Another challenge of private universities is improving the quality of education in all subjects and courses. The quality is measured in university examinations will be based on the percentage of students clearing/complying with the degree requirements in the minimum graduation time. As per requirement at least 80% students should graduate in minimum time to score maximum marks.

2. Competitive Examination:

Student's performance in public examinations (such as UPSC, State PSCs, SSC, GATE, NET, CAT, BASRB, civil services etc.) from the university will be counted for the ranking. Such challenge will lead to improvement in teaching – learning model by emphasizing multiple choice questions in each chapter of the subjects studying in a course. Based on this concept of ranking, private universities have to make modifications in university examination patterns by adding 50% weightage to multiple choice questions in question papers. The university also has challenge in adding public examination subjects in its course as value addition.

(d) Outreach and Inclusivity :

1. Continuing Education & Services :

The university has to organize various refresher and orientation courses for its alumni, industries, and attract more participants in each programme. Compulsory Teacher quality improvement Training and related outreach activities are also have to be organized to keep teachers updated.

The university also has to focus on e-content creation (in text, audio and video format) on all subjects of all courses to support its students. Private universities have challenge in including

industries in curriculum design, curriculum delivery, and examination systems to create industry acceptable graduates.

2. Percentage of Students from Other States & Countries :

To maintain regional diversity in the campus, private universities have a challenge to develop a strategy to attract and admit students from other states and countries. The university shall conduct entrance exams in many centres in different states of the country and even in other potential countries by giving enough publicity.

3. Percentage of Women Students and Faculty :

To main gender equality, private university has a challenge in identifying and appointing women faculties and women students to the courses such that 50% women students and 20% women faculty and two (2) women as Institute Head or in the Governing Board are required to get maximum score.

4. Percentage of Economically and Socially Disadvantaged Students :

The university has a challenge to admit students from economically and socially backward communities by identifying deserved students. The private universities should reserve finance from their budget for such social service. The challenge is to create provision for admitting 50% economically and socially disadvantaged students to all courses by providing subsidy/scholarship to such students to score maximum marks.

5. Facilities for Differently Abled Persons :

To attract and provide suitable facilities to differently abled persons (both faculty & students) the university should make renovation in existing buildings or design/re-design future constructions by adding ramps, lifts, disabled friendly toilets. They also have to provide walking aids, Braille / Special Labs, and Audio Visual Aids to such people.

(e) Perception

1. Process for Peer Rating in Category :

Peer rating is to be done through a survey conducted over a large category of academics, institution heads, HR heads of employers, members of funding agencies in Government, Private sector, NGOs, etc. Feedback of faculty, students and other stakeholders will be also considered for such peer rating. To score well in such process, private universities should focus on continuous improvements and student and faculty friendly environment in the campus. They should involve local industries, feeding colleges in various innovative programmes conducted by both student union and University administration.

2. Application to Seat Ratio :

Private universities even though new in the higher education institutions category, face challenge to attract students for admission. Based on quality, infrastructure, teaching-learning & examination innovations, and good placements, they create brand which attracts many student aspirants to increase application to seat ratio. The university gets better ranking and status, based on its score, which is calculated by considering total number of seats in UG and PG programmes divided by total number of applications received considering all UG and PG Programs.

VI. Conclusion

In this paper we have analyzed the Challenges and Opportunities of private universities for imparting Higher Education in terms of Establishment, Admission Designing courses & Curriculum, Innovations in teaching & learning processes, Research & development, Industry & Foreign Collaborations, Usage of ICT, Student support & Progression, Expansion to global market, Governance, Leadership and Management, Innovations & Best practices etc. The Advantages, Benefits, Constraints, and Disadvantages of Private Universities for its stakeholders like students, faculty members, parents, industries and society are also studied. Finally, the opportunities and challenges of National Institutional Ranking framework under five stated criteria are analysed in detail. Based on above analysis it is found that there are more opportunities and challenges to the private universities under advantages and benefits than constraints and disadvantages to its stakeholders.

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